

THEORETICAL SENSITIVITY OF COMPOSITE CYLINDERS IN COMPRESSION TO FILAMENT-WINDING PATTERN

David W. Jensen and Suresh P. Pai

The Pennsylvania State University, Department of Aerospace Engineering
233-N Hammond Building, University Park, PA 16802 USA

ABSTRACT

This work illustrates the influence of elastic couplings on the compressive stability of filament-wound cylinders. In particular, the number of diamond-shaped repeating units around the circumference was varied in numerical simulations based on the finite element method. The material constitutive behavior in the undulation regions is different from that in the alternating, antisymmetric, triangular, flat plate regions. The elastic couplings introduced by the tow crossovers are approximated by averaging the elastic coupling stiffness terms over half of the undulation length. The resulting elastic buckling loads and mode shapes show a strong dependence on the number of diamond-shaped repeating units around the circumference. The results from this analysis demonstrate the significance of the elastic couplings and the scale of the winding pattern on the compressive stability of filament-wound cylinders.

Keywords: Buckling, Filament-Winding, Cylinder

1. INTRODUCTION

Filament-wound cylinders offer considerable potential for employment as primary structural members in various aerospace applications, such as aircraft fuselages and rocket motor casings. The filament-wound cylinders provide designers with a host of design parameters such as winding angles, layup sequence, fiber tow width, and fiber-crossover band spacing (dimensions of the diamond-shaped repeating patterns). These parameters in turn provide considerable flexibility in the design of filament-wound cylinders. In addition to the advantages of high specific strength and stiffness found in all composites, the highly automated fabrication process of filament-winding can be quite cost effective.

The effects of the manufacturing parameters, however, need to be quantified in order to verify each design. Experimental and analytical investigations on buckling of filament-wound cylindrical shells under axial compression have been reported by Tasi [1], Card [2], Khot [3], Hirano [4], and others. These authors assumed the shells to be homogeneous, without discussing the elastic coupling effects on buckling stresses. Jones [5] analyzed the coupling effect only for crossply laminated cylinders. Uemura [6] addressed the coupling effects on the axial buckling stresses of the cross-ply and angle-ply laminated composite cylinders simply supported at both ends. This research shows that the magnitude of elastic stiffness couplings is an extremely important factor in the compressive stability of filament-wound cylinders. Hipp [7] showed that the accuracy of theoretical predictions is enhanced when the stiffness coupling effects of fiber crossovers is considered while analyzing filament-wound cylinders.

The occurrence of fiber crossovers is inherent in the filament-winding process. The sinusoidal geometry of the undulating fibers in the tow crossover regions results in the introduction of elastic stiffness couplings. The tow crossover regions form the borders of the diamond-shaped patterns which characterize filament-wound cylinders (see Figure 1). This work illustrates the influence of elastic couplings on the compressive stability of filament-wound cylinders. In particular, the number of diamond-shaped repeating units around the circumference was varied in numerical simulations based on the finite element method. The material constitutive behavior in the undulation regions is different from that in the alternating, antisymmetric, triangular, flat plate regions. The elastic couplings introduced by the tow crossovers are approximated by averaging the elastic coupling stiffness terms derived from a three-dimensional local micromechanics model over one half of the undulation length. All cylinders simulated in the present study have a single filament-wound layer with a winding angle of $\pm 30^\circ$

Figure 1: Filament-Wound Cylinder Geometry

2. MICROMECHANICS MODEL OF FIBER CROSSOVER

The micromechanics model of the fiber crossover region was based on the fiber crossover geometry identified in Figure 2 [8]. Photomicrographs of a fiber tow taken from manufactured cylinders were used to identify the actual undulation geometry shown in Figure 2c. The three-dimensional fiber crossover region is represented by the rectangular parallelepiped (a-b-c-d-e-f-g-h) shown in Figure 2d. The undulation geometry of the fiber crossover in the filament-wound cylinder was approximated with the Crimp model developed for woven fabric composites by Chou and Ishikawa [9]. A modified undulation shape and three-dimensional stiffness transformations were introduced into the Crimp model to describe the filament-wound undulation cell. In this model, the midsurface shape of the undulating fiber tow is approximated by:

$$h_u(x) = \frac{h}{2} \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{L_u}\right) \quad (1)$$

where $h_u(x)$ is the centerline of the undulating fiber tow, h is the thickness of the fiber tow, x is the distance along the undulation, and L_u is the length of the undulation region. The inclination angle, θ , of the undulating layer with respect to the horizontal plane at a particular location is given by:

$$\theta = \text{Arctan}\left(\frac{dh_u}{dx}\right) \quad (2)$$

Fibers in the undulating layer are also oriented at an angle, ψ , with respect to the x-z plane of the rectangular parallelepiped a-b-c-d-e-f-g-h (see Figure 2b,d) given by:

$$\psi = 90 - 2\phi \quad (3)$$

where ϕ is the helical-winding angle (30° in this study). Hence, the mechanical stiffness terms are evaluated in the structural coordinates of the parallelepiped by transforming the transversely isotropic material properties of the undulating tow through two angles; namely, $-\theta$ and $-\psi$. The transformed three-dimensional stiffness coefficients, C_{ij} , for the undulating tows were reduced to the two-dimensional

Figure 2: Sketch of Tow Crossover Geometry

form, Q^* , using the assumptions of classical plate theory; namely, $\gamma_{xz} = \gamma_{yz} = \sigma_z = 0$, resulting in:

$$Q_{ij}^* = c_{ij} - \frac{c_{i3} c_{3j}}{c_{33}} \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6) \quad (4)$$

The effective plane stress stiffness coefficient matrix, Q^* , was used to calculate the two-dimensional stretching, coupling and bending stiffness matrices. Lamination theory was assumed to be applicable at discrete locations along the undulation. The effective A, B, and D matrices for the undulation region were calculated by averaging the values obtained from integrating over half the undulation length. This preserves the bending-extension coupling (B) caused by the antisymmetrical geometry, which would otherwise vanish if averaged over the entire length. The matrices were then transformed back into the global coordinates of the cylinder using the transformation angle ($\alpha = 90 - \phi$). The transversely isotropic properties of a graphite/epoxy composite used to calculate the stiffness matrices are summarized in Table 1.

Classical lamination theory (CLT) was used to find the A, B, and D matrices of the alternating, antisymmetric, triangular, flat plate regions. The stiffness values of the plate and undulation regions are summarized in Table 2. These stiffness values were used as material properties in the finite element models of the filament-wound cylinder. CLT predicts that most of the coupling stiffness terms (namely, A_{16} , A_{26} , B_{11} , B_{12} , B_{22} , B_{66} , D_{16} , and D_{26}) are identically zero. On the other hand, the coupling terms in the undulation region are not zero. The plate regions, however, have higher values of stretching-twisting and bending-shearing couplings (B_{16} and B_{26}) than the tow undulation regions due to averaging in the Fiber Crimp model.

Table 1: Graphite/Epoxy Material Properties

PROPERTY	VALUE
E_1	19.4×10^6 (Psi)
E_2	1.4×10^6 (Psi)
ν_{12}	0.3
ν_{23}	0.03
G_{12}	0.8×10^6 (Psi)

Table 2: Stiffness Values for Laminate and Undulation Regions

LAMINATE REGION			UNDULATION REGION		
Stretching Stiffness ($A - \text{lb/in}$) $\times 10^3$ Matrices					
233.23	70.67	0.0	229.62	69.49	-1.55
	55.06	0.0		54.66	-0.59
Symmetric		78.22	Symmetric		77.0
Stretching-Bending Coupling ($B - \text{lb}$) $\times 10^0$ Matrices					
0.0	0.0	565.4	-9.62	-3.60	356.8
	0.0	206.2		-1.40	130.3
Symmetric		0.0	Symmetric		-2.81
Bending Stiffness ($D - \text{lb.in}$) $\times 10^0$ Matrices					
7.78	2.36	0.0	7.73	2.34	1.43
	1.84	0.0		1.83	0.52
Symmetric		2.61	Symmetric		2.59

3. FINITE ELEMENT MODELS OF FILAMENT-WOUND CYLINDERS

Five finite element models (shown in Figure 3), each with a different number of diamond-shaped repeating units around the circumference, were developed and subjected to simulated compression using ABAQUS® software. The buckling loads were determined using the eigenvalue buckling analysis. Each of the 25.4 cm (10") long by 15.2 cm (6") diameter cylindrical models employed a single filament-wound layer oriented at $\pm 30^\circ$, with the diamond patterns placed symmetrically about the $R-\theta$ midplane (perpendicular to the longitudinal axis of the cylinder). A Fortran preprocessor was written to generate the nodal location and element connectivity for the various finite element models. The models employ eight-noded quadrilateral shell elements (designated S8R5) based on thin shell theory, with the Kirchoff assumptions algebraically imposed in the development of the stiffness matrix [10].

Figure 3: Finite Element Models for Different Circumferential Patterns

The finite element model details are presented in Table 3, where N_d represents the number of diamond repeating patterns around the circumference. Two different meshes were employed for the cylinder with four circumferential repeating units to evaluate mesh convergence.

Table 3: Finite Element Model Details

N_d	Elements	Nodes
4	288	912
4	584	1816
5	360	1140
6	432	1368
7	840	2604
8	960	2976

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Investigation of Elastic Coupling Effects

The effect of elastic couplings, a critical factor governing buckling behavior, was studied using the cylindrical model with four circumferential repeating units. Four different sets of material constitutive properties based on the A, B, and D laminate stiffness matrices were analyzed and compared (see Table 4). First, the entire cylinder was modelled using the A, B, and D matrices of a

Table 4: Description of Different Material Data Sets

MATERIAL SET	DESCRIPTION
1	$\pm 30^\circ$ Laminate
2	Alternating $\pm 30^\circ$ & $\mp 30^\circ$ Laminates
3	Set 2 with Modified Undulation Properties
4	Set 3 with Undulation B_{16} & B_{26} replaced by Laminate Values

$\pm 30^\circ$ laminate, based on classical lamination theory. Next, the A, B, and D for alternating $\pm 30^\circ$ and $\mp 30^\circ$ laminates were used in the two halves of each diamond repeating pattern. Third, the modified A, B, and D matrices for the fiber undulation regions were used in the helical and circumferential fiber crossover regions in addition to the alternating $\pm 30^\circ$ and $\mp 30^\circ$ laminate properties in the interior regions. Here, it is to be noted that the stretching-twisting/bending-shearing coupling values (B_{16} and B_{26}) in the undulation regions are less than those for the corresponding flat (antisymmetric) laminates. This decrease is brought about by the averaging of the properties. Hence, in the fourth set of material properties, the maximum values of the B_{16} and B_{26} terms (i.e., the same as in the flat laminate regions) are used in the undulation regions.

The buckling loads for each of the different material data sets are summarized in Table 5, where the subscripts indicate the mesh number. It can be observed that the finite element model predicts a maximum buckling load when the stiffness properties of only the $\pm 30^\circ$ laminate are included. It is interesting to note that the buckling load predicted for material set 2 (alternating $\pm 30^\circ$ and $\mp 30^\circ$ laminate properties) is lower than that predicted for material set 3 (alternating $\pm 30^\circ$ and $\mp 30^\circ$ laminate properties with the modified undulation properties). This implies that the stretching-twisting/bending-shearing couplings (B_{16} and B_{26}) in an antisymmetric laminate tend to decrease the buckling load to a greater extent than the other coupling terms introduced by the fiber undulations. Finally, although it represents a fictitious situation, the finite element model predicts the lowest buckling load when the maximum elastic couplings, from a combination of the antisymmetric laminate and fiber undulation, are included in the model.

Table 5: Summary of Buckling Loads

N_d	Buckling Load (lbs)			
	Set 1	Set 2	Set 3	Set 4
4_1				3170
4_2	4560	4090	4230	3500
5_1		3590	4090	3006
6_1		3570	3850	2980
7_1			3870	2610
8_1			3910	2610

4.2. Investigation of Diamond-Shaped Pattern Size Effects

The dependence of the buckling load on the number of diamond-shaped repeating units around the circumference is also summarized in Table 5 and shown graphically in Figure 4. The buckling mode shapes are shown in Figure 5. In the case of set 3 material properties ($\pm 30^\circ$ and $\mp 30^\circ$ laminate with modified undulation properties), the buckling load is lowest for a cylinder with six diamond-shaped repeating units around the circumference. This variation in the buckling load can be explained on the basis of interaction between the geometric influence on the buckling mode shape and the diamond-

Figure 4: Variation of Buckling Load With Number of Circumferential Repeating Units

Figure 5: Midsection View of Buckling Mode Shapes for Different Circumferential Patterns

shaped pattern. In Figure 5, it can be seen that the mode shape has a ridge and valley pattern which closely follows the diamond-shaped repeating pattern. For the cylinder with six circumferential units, the buckling mode shape is very close to one of the natural mode shapes of a cylinder with a uniform $\pm 30^\circ$ layup. In the other cylinders, the shape of the repeating unit forces a buckling mode shape which is quite different from the geometrically-driven mode shape of a cylinder with a uniform $\pm 30^\circ$ layup. The trends observed in the case of buckling loads of cylinders with set 3 material properties are similar to the trends observed in experiments reported in Reference [11]. This trend, however, is not evident in the models based on material property set 4 ($\pm 30^\circ$ and $\mp 30^\circ$ laminate properties with modified undulation properties and maximum B_{16} and B_{26} couplings).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The material couplings introduced by the undulating tows in filament-wound cylinders have been shown to significantly influence the compressive stability (buckling). Accounting for the material couplings in the tow crossover region and using the maximum values of the B_{16} and B_{26} couplings from the alternating, antisymmetric, triangular, flat plate regions provides the most conservative estimate of the buckling load. Furthermore, the buckling mode shapes and, hence, the critical loads are strongly influenced by the number of diamond-shaped repeating units around the circumference of the cylinder. The results from this analysis demonstrate the significance of the elastic couplings and the scale of the winding pattern on the compressive stability of filament-wound cylinders.

REFERENCES

1. Tasi, J., Feldman, A., and Stang, D. A., *The Buckling Strength of Filament-Wound Cylinders Loaded in Axial Compression*, NASA CR-266, 1965.
2. Card, M. F., *Experiments to Determine the Strength of Filament-Wound Cylinders Loaded in Axial Compression*, NASA TN D-3522, 1966.
3. Khot, N. S., *Buckling and Postbuckling Behavior of Composite Cylindrical Shells Under Axial Compression*, *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 8, No. 2, 1970, pp. 229-235.
4. Hirano, Y., *Buckling of Angle-Ply Laminated Circular Cylindrical Shells*, *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 46, 1979, pp. 233-234.
5. Jones, R. M. and Morgan, H. S., *Buckling and Vibration of Cross-Ply Laminated Circular Cylindrical Shells*, *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 13, No. 5, 1975, pp. 664-671.
6. Uemura, M. and Kasuya, H., *Coupling Effects on Axial Compressive Buckling of Laminated Composite Cylindrical Shells*, *Progress in Science and Engineering of Composites*, ICCM-IV, Ed. T. Hayasi, K. Kawata, and S. Umekawa, Tokyo, 1982, pp. 583-590.
7. Hipp, P. A. and Jensen, D. W., *Design and Analysis of Filament-Wound Cylinders in Compression*, *Proceedings of the 33rd AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference*, Dallas, TX, April 1992, pp. 2442-2452.
8. Jensen, D. W. and Pai, S. P., *Influence of Fiber Undulations on the Buckling Behavior of Filament-Wound Cylinders*, *ASC Proceedings of the 7th Technical Conference on Composite Materials*, The Pennsylvania State University, Pennsylvania, October, 1992, pp. 672-681.
9. Chou, T. W. and Ishikawa, T., *Analysis and Modelling of 2-Dimensional Fabric Composites*, *Textile Structural Composites*, T. W. Chou and F. Ko, Eds., Elsevier Science Publishing Co., New York, 1989.
10. ABAQUS User's Manual, Version 4-8, Hibbit-Karlson-Sorensen Inc., 1990.
11. Claus, S. J., *The Effects of Winding Pattern on the Compressive Behavior of Filament-Wound Cylinders*, *ASC Proceedings of the 7th Technical Conference on Composite Materials*, The Pennsylvania State University, Pennsylvania, October, 1992, pp. 258-265.